
SPECIAL LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS SATISFACTION ON ORGANIZATIONAL TRAINING FACILITIES: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

The fast changing technological developments made the existing knowledge of special library professionals ineffective, which they had at the time of entering into the organization. Hence, professionals have to be trained to operate new techniques and equipments, to handle the Present as well as new jobs more effectively. Training is useful not only for the organizations, but also for the employees as it develops knowledge, problem-solving ability and skill of the newly recruited employees on the one hand and serves as a refresher course in updating old employees on the other hand. It aims at improving the organization's performance through the enhanced performance of its employees. Because of these reasons training has become an integral part of human resource development in special libraries. Knowing this fact following study has been carried out to know the special library professional's level of satisfaction on training and development provided in organization.

Keywords: Training; Special library; Media library; Software Industry Library Satisfaction; Research and Developmental library; Job Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Special libraries are always been concerned with the collection, organization, storage and retrieval of recent and special information, in order to respond to user's queries. It was also often been noted that new technologies for the generation, distribution, processing and storage of information have brought changes in the nature, volume, and format of that information. So it creates increased pressure over the years. This increasing pressure can be controlled from giving adequate training to library professionals at regular intervals. Training of library and information professionals in developed countries such as the U.K., the U.S.A., Australia, Canada and developing countries like India has also supported such demand. Training of library and information professionals in India has been made important in recent years by creating the good training infrastructure in professionals (Paul, 2014). The main objective of the training is to enhance competencies, upgrade the skills and improve the ability and efficiency of Library

professionals in use of modern information technology and its application in their respective libraries Chand and Dheer, (2009). While training is positively associated with the employee job satisfaction and employee job satisfaction is further having relationship with the measures of performance. Training brings the change in employee attitude which is consistently (Rowden, 2003). It is one of the means of improving the manpower utilization and helps the potential raise in the employee's job satisfaction. Knowing these facts present study has been undertaken to identify the library professional's satisfaction on training and development in Indian special libraries.

2. Concept and Definition

Training is a process of assisting a person in enhancing his efficiency and effectiveness at work by improving and up-grading his knowledge, developing skills relevant to his work and cultivating appropriate attitudes and behavior towards work. Training could be existing capabilities for preparing a person for still higher responsibilities which may call for new knowledge and skills.

According to Paul Training may be defined as systematized tailor-made performance to suit the needs of a particular organization for developing certain attitudes, action, skills and abilities in employees irrespective of their functional levels (Paul, 2002).

According to Landy training is "a set of planned activities on the part of an organization to increase the job knowledge and skills or to modify the attitudes and social behavior of its embers in ways consistent with the goals of the organization and the requirements of the job".

3. Objectives

The specific objectives of the study were as follows:

- 1) To identify the special professionals satisfaction on training facilities provided in organization.
- 2) To be acquainted with the establishment of training department in organization.
- 3) To make out the male and female professionals ration in Special libraries.
- 4) To find out the social background and marital status of Special libraries.
- 5) To determine the training frequency in Special libraries.
- 6) To identify the association between media, software and R &D library professionals on training.

4. Need of Training in Special Libraries

The need of this study is to assess the training and development facilities provided in special libraries in Karnataka State with a view of identify nature of training, frequency of training and making the necessary recommendations for their resolution.

5. Literature Review

Literature review is process of reviewing critically examines the different works already conducted by different researcher. It helps to measure the quality of work and useful to conduct the research efficiently and effectively. The following literature is obtained by scanning through the various sources like books, journal articles, databases, conference proceedings, theses dissertations etc.

Spector (1997) study revealed that that the employees who are satisfied with their job perform noticeable better than those who are unsatisfied. There is a wide range of driving forces of job satisfaction; employee training is one of them. He also stressed that training enhances the commitment of employee with the organization. Training deals with the efforts made to bring improvement in the performance of employees. Satisfaction with training and development is a major factor in decision regarding people's career. Violin's (2001) North American Review Survey of twenty six hundred American and Canadian employees found that 80% of respondents said receiving training that increases their skills and abilities was a key component of what they looked for in jobs.

Baldwin & Johnson (1995) study identified training is the best solution to improve employee's understanding and let them know how to use the specific skills. Training can also be of general in nature which enhances employee's skills to cope with the common problems. There are few factors which have string impact on the output of training. Employee training persistently contributes to the increase in capital stock which is available in the economy

Chand and Dheer (2009) found that aim of training is to enhance competencies, upgrade the skills and improve the ability and efficiency of Library professionals in use of modern information technology and its application in their respective libraries While training is positively associated with the employee job satisfaction and employee job satisfaction is further having relationship with the measures of performance. Training brings the change in employee attitude which is consistently (Rowden, 2003). It is one of the means of improving the manpower utilization and helps the potential raise in the employee's job satisfaction. However, it need employees should be given opportunity to grow in the professional environment, when they are provided latest tools, experience trainer and proper on the job and on the job training.

According to Pan & Hovde (2010) training need is motivated by both the "technological imperative" thus the rapid technological change that characterizes contemporary academic libraries, and by the element that librarians and information workers share with other professionals, that they are compensated for what they know as well as for what they do. Olaniyan and Ojo (2008) highlighted some of the benefits to be deprival from training staff in any organization. Skills, Increase productivity, improve the quality of work develop new knowledge understanding and attitudes etc.

6. Scope and Limitation of the Study

The present study is designed to analysis of training and development trends in special libraries. The study is confined to Software Industry/Information Technology (IT)/corporate libraries,

Research and Development libraries (R & D) (including institutes of national importance and industries) and media libraries of both government and private sectors of Karnataka state.

7. Methodology

In order to achieve the objectives of the study survey research and questionnaire method was used for this study. Data is collected mainly from primary source. A structured close ended questionnaire was designed for the study and it was distributed among special library professionals of Karnataka State.

8. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The researcher attempted to ensure a sample that would represent the population and hence selected simple random method for the study. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and were given enough time to go through it and respond to the questions therein. The data collected were tabulated and analyzed statistically using appropriate descriptive techniques included in Software Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) V.20.

Table 1: Distribution of Questionnaire and Response Received

Nature of Library		Number of Questionnaires		Percentage of Response
		Distributed	Received	
Media Library	Count	34	29	85.2%
Software Library	Count	80	57	71.3%
Research Library	Count	216	189	87.5%
Total		330	275	83.3%

Table-1 illustrates that among total of 330 professionals, 330 questionnaires were distributed and managed to collect 275 filled questionnaires back with overall response rate of 83.33%. Further, in case of media, software industry and R & D libraries, 85.2%, 71.3% and 87.5% of response is achieved respectively.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Nature of Library		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Media Library	Count & %	18 (62.1%)	11 (37.9%)	29 (100%)
	Total %	6.5%	4.0%	10.5%
Software Library	Count & %	33 (57.9%)	24 (42.1%)	57 (100%)
	Total %	12.0%	8.7%	20.7%
Research Library	Count & %	102 (54%)	87 (46%)	189 (100%)
	Total %	37.1%	31.6%	68.7%
Total		153 (55.6%)	122 (44.4%)	275 (100%)

It is observed from the table and graph-1 that, out of the total 275 respondents majority 153 (55.6%) of respondents belongs to male category and 122 (44.4%) of respondents are females category. It is further observed from the above table that, in media, software and R & D libraries

18 (62.1%), 33 (57.9%), 102 (54%) of respondents are male and 11 (37.9%), 24 (42.1%) and 87 (46%) of respondents are female respectively.

Bellow table-3 articulates that majority of 235 (85.5%) respondents are married and 40 (14.5%) are un-married. It is also observed that highest number of married respondents has comparatively at the forefront over unmarried respondents in media libraries 28 (96.6%), software industry libraries 49 (86%) and R & D libraries 158 (83.6%) respectively.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

Nature of Library		Marital Status		Total
		Married	Unmarried	
Media Library	Count & %	28 (96.6%)	1 (3.4%)	29 (100%)
	Total %	10.2%	0.4%	10.5%
Software Library	Count & %	49 (86%)	8 (14%)	57 (100%)
	Total %	17.8%	2.9%	20.7%
Research Library	Count & %	158 (83.6%)	31 (16.4%)	189 (100%)
	Total %	57.5%	11.3%	68.7%
Total		235 (85.5%)	40 (14.5%)	275 (100%)

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Social Background

Nature of Library		Social Background			Total
		Urban	Semi-urban	Rural	
Media Library	Count & %	6 (20.7%)	12 (41.4%)	11 (37.9%)	29 (100%)
	Total %	2.2%	4.4%	4%	10.5%
Software Library	Count & %	15 (26.3%)	26 (45.6%)	16 (28.1%)	57 (100%)
	Total %	5.5%	9.5%	5.8%	20.7%
Research Library	Count & %	88 (46.6%)	55 (29.1%)	46 (24.3%)	189 (100%)
	Total %	32%	20%	16.7%	68.7%
Total		109 (39.6%)	93 (33.8%)	73 (26.5%)	275 (100%)

Graph1: Distribution of Respondents by Social Background

It is clear from table-4 and Graph-1 highest number 109 (39.6%) of professionals are belongs to urban category preceded by 93(33.8%) are semi-urban and 73 (26.5%) of rural background. It is further identifies that maximum number of media library 12 (41.4%) and 26 (45.6%) of software industry professionals are belongs to semi-urban category but in case of R & D libraries majority of 88 (46.6%) of professionals belongs to urban background.

Table 5: Essentialness of Professional Training

Nature of Library		Professional Training Essential			Total
		<i>Highly Essential</i>	<i>Essential</i>	<i>Not Essential</i>	
Media Library	<i>Count & %</i>	3 (10.3%)	21 (72.4%)	5 (17.2%)	29 (100%)
	<i>% of Total</i>	1.1%	7.6%	1.8%	10.5%
Software Library	<i>Count & %</i>	30 (52.6%)	18 (31.6%)	9 (15.8%)	57 (100%)
	<i>% of Total</i>	10.9%	6.5%	3.3%	20.7%
R & D Library	<i>Count & %</i>	80 (42.3%)	70 (37%)	39 (20.6%)	189 (100%)
	<i>% of Total</i>	29.1%	25.5%	14.2%	68.7%
Grand Total		113 (41.1%)	109 (39.6%)	53 (19.3%)	275 (100%)

Chi-Square Tests for Essentialness of Professional Training

Test	Value	Df (Degree of Freedom)	Result
Pearson Chi-Square	18.309 ^a	4	.001
N of Valid Cases	275		

In above table obtained chi-squared value is 18.309 which is greater than the theoretical table value 14.860 at 0.05 level of significance, so it can be concluded that, “opinion towards essentialness of professional training among special library professionals is differ.

It depicts from the table-5 that, majority 113 (41.1%) of professionals strongly opined professional training program is highly essential to perform work in organization followed by 109 (39.6%) of respondents opined essential and finally 53 (19.3%) of respondents felt training is not essential. It is also observed that among three different special libraries maximum number 21 (72.4%) of media library, 30 (52.6%) of software industry library and 80 (42.3%) of R and D library professionals felt professional training is highly essential.

In table-7 obtained chi-squared value is 66.140 which is greater than the theoretical table value 10.597 at 0.05 level of significance, so it can be concluded that “opinion towards existence of training department in respective organization among special library professionals is differ.

Data shown in table-7 describes that almost among total respondents almost half 139 (50.5%) of the respondents opined existence of separate training department in organization and remaining 103 (37.4%) of respondents doesn't have separate training department. Among three different nature of special libraries maximum number of media library 23 (79.3%) respondents opined doesn't have separate training department. In case of R & D libraries exactly equal proportion 78 (41.2%) of respondents' opined existence and not existence of separate training department in respective organization. But in software industry libraries highest number of 55 (96.5%) respondents expressed existence of separate training department in their organization.

Table 7: Distribution of Respondents on Existence of Training Department in Organization

Nature of Library		Existence of Training Department			Total
		Yes	No	NA	
Media Library	Count & %	6 (20.7%)	23 (79.3%)	0 (0%)	29 (100%)
	% of Total	2.2%	8.4%	0%	10.5%
Software Library	Count & %	55 (96.5%)	2 (3.5%)	0 (0%)	57 (100%)
	% of Total	20%	0.7%	0%	20.7%
R & D Library	Count & %	78 (41.3%)	78 (41.3%)	33 (17.5%)	189 (100%)
	% of Total	28.4%	28.3%	12%	68.7%
Total		139 (50.5%)	103 (37.4%)	33 (12%)	275 (100%)

Chi-Square Tests for Existence of Training Department

Test	Value	Df (Degree of Freedom)	Result
Pearson Chi-Square	64.983 ^a	2	.000
N of Valid Cases	275		

Table 8: Satisfaction on Existing Training provided

Nature of Library		Satisfaction on Existing Training			Total
		Yes	No	NA	
Media Library	Count & %	22 (75.9%)	7 (24.1%)	0 (0%)	29 (100%)
	Total %	8%	2.5%	0%	10.5%
Software Library	Count & %	56 (98.2%)	1 (1.8%)	0 (0%)	57 (100%)
	Total %	20.4%	0.4%	0%	20.7%
R & D Library	Count & %	130 (68.7%)	26 (13.7%)	33 (17.5%)	189 (100%)
	Total %	47.2%	6.54%	12%	68.7%
Grand Total		208 (75.6%)	34 (12.3%)	33 (12%)	275 (100%)

Chi-Square Tests for Satisfaction on Existing Training provided

Test	Value	Df (Degree of Freedom)	Result
Pearson Chi-Square	16.845 ^a	4	.002
N of Valid Cases	275		

In above table obtained chi-squared value is 16.845 which is greater than the theoretical table value 14.860 at 0.05 level of significance so it can be concluded that, "opinion towards satisfaction on existing training among special library professionals is differ.

Table-8 clearly portrays that majority of 208 (75.6%) respondents expressed their satisfaction on training facility provided and 34 (12.3%) of respondents expressed their dissatisfaction on training facility of the organization. Further it can be also found that among three different nature of special libraries majority of media library 22 (75.9%) of respondents, 56 (98.2%) of software industry libraries and finally 130 (68.7%) of R & D respondents expressed their satisfaction on existing training facility provided from respective special libraries.

9. Findings of the Study

- Majority of 235 (85.5%) respondents are belongs to married 40 (14.5%) category. The reason for majority in married respondents is because of among total number of 275 respondents 92.7% of the respondents are belongs to the age group of above 31 years and as per Indian standard average age of marriage is 27 years.
- Software industry libraries are giving more importance to training than media and R & D libraries.
- Out of 275 respondents more than two third of respondents expressed their satisfaction on existing training facility provided by their organizations.
- There is a significant difference between special libraries on essentialness of training, existence of training department and satisfaction on training and development facilities provided by organization.
- More than one third of the respondent's organization doesn't have separate training department in organization.
- More than one third of respondents 109 (39.6%) were from urban background, indicating that management education remained confined in hands of the elite urban masses.

10. Recommendations

- Need to increase training programs in special libraries particularly in media and R & D libraries in particular.
- There is an immediate need to improve training facilities in special libraries in general and research and development libraries in particular.
- Measures should be taken to identify the training needs of the professionals.

11. Conclusion

In the age of digital environment, the special library professionals also realize the need to develop and provide up-to date information service to meet the requirements of the users. Training helps the special professionals in acquiring knowledge of the subject matter, bridging the gap between past and present, enhancing the capability of the trainees, developing knowledge

according to the new environment and brings out a change of attitude and behavior to fulfill the needs of users. Hence training is positively associated with the employee job satisfaction and employee job satisfaction is further having relationship with the measures of performance. Training brings the change in employee attitude which is consistently.

References

- [1] Chand, Salek and Dheer, Lalita (2009). Training: A Technique for Empowerment of Library professionals Talent Development and Strategies, ICAL, p. 356-360.
- [2] Chhabra, T.N. Human Resource Management-Concepts and Issues, 4th edition, Shamp Co. Delhi.
- [3] John, R., Baldwin and Jaonne Johnson (1995), "Human Capital Development and Innovation: The case of training in small and medium sized – firm
- [4] Frank J. Landy, Jeffrey M. Conte Work in the 21st Century: An Introduction to Industrial and Organizational Psychology, 5th Ed. Wiley. New Jersey
- [5] Natrajan, M. (2008). Training needs for Library professionals: Current & future pattern. International Conference .NEHU, Shillong.
- [6] Olaniyan D. A & Ojo, L. (2008). Staff training and development: A vital tool for organizational effectiveness. Euro Journals 24(3):326-331.
- [7] Pan, J. & Hovde, K. (2010). Professional Development for Academic Librarians: Needs, Resources, and Administrative Support. Chinese Librarianship: an International Electronic Journal, 29. URL: <http://www.iclc.us/cliej/cl29PH.htm26>
- [8] Paul, N.K. (2002). Manpower training in University Libraries with special reference to North-Eastern Hill University Library and Assam University Library: A study, Un-published dissertation report, Gauhati University, pp. 6.
- [9] Paul, N.K. (2014). A Study of the effects of Manpower training and job satisfaction of the library professionals in North East India, Assam University, PhD thesis. Pp.165-204
- [10] Spector, P. E. (1997). Job satisfaction application assessment: Causes and consequences, Thousand oaks', Calif, Sage Publications.
- [11] Rowden, R.W. & Conine Jr.C-T (2003), The Relationship between workplace learning and job satisfaction in U.S. Small Commercial Bank. In S.A. Lynna & T.M. Egan (Eds.) AHRD, Conference Proceedings (pp. 459-466).
- [12] Violino, B. (2001). Still the Money Network Computing, 12 (16), 66.
- [13] <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/205/10/10>

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